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FICTITIOUS MICROORGANISMS: LACERDA AND THE DISCOVERY OF *BACILLUS BERIBERICUS*

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Abstract: In the late 19th century, beriberi was a serious disease in Brazil. Several different causes were ascribed to that malady, including miasma infection, undernourishment, food poisoning, contagion, and changes of weather. In 1883, the Brazilian physician João Batista de Lacerda (1846-1915) began experimental investigation of microorganisms as possible cause of beriberi. He attempted to follow Pasteur's and Koch's method. Lacerda reported the finding of a microorganism he called *Bacillus beribericus* in the blood of beriberi patients. He claimed that he had been able to cultivate those microorganisms and to produce beriberi in healthy animals by inoculating that culture. Lacerda's work was criticized both in Brazil and abroad. Other researchers claimed similar discoveries, including Cornelis Pekelharing, in India. The paper discusses the method used by Lacerda. It is shown that he was unable to follow the rigorous method prescribed by Robert Koch.

Keywords: Lacerda, João Batista de; beriberi; microbe theory; Koch's method

1. INTRODUCTION

The second half of the 19th century witnessed the first great successes of the microbiological theory of diseases. It seemed that at last, after thousand years of darkness, Medicine had found a safe, scientific method for its development.

Excessive optimism and exaggerated confidence on the microbe theory led, however, to serious mistakes. Careful researches (such as those of Robert Koch) had shown that some diseases were produced by microorganisms. This led, however, to a widespread belief that all diseases are caused by microbes. To many physicians of the late 19th century, it seemed that medical research had been reduced to the search for pathological microorganisms (together with their eventual vectors) and the development of vaccines.

Nowadays we know that some diseases are caused by nutritional deficiency¹. It is not enough to eat a large amount of food – it must be of the right kind. A suitable equilibrium of protein,

¹ For a general review of the development of nutritional research up to the beginning of the 20th century, see Mccollum (1957) and Santos (1989).

carbohydrate and fat is a condition of health. Besides that, there are some substances – *vitamins*² – that are also essential: their lack produces diseases such as scurvy and beriberi. The role of vitamins, however, was only discovered in the 20th century.

The series of trials and mistakes that led to the understanding of the causal role of food deficiency in beriberi has been described several times in the historiographic literature (see, for instance, Scott, 1939, vol. 2, pp. 858-97; Ihde & Becker, 1971; Codell Carter, 1977). The aim of this paper is not to review that history, but to describe a particular episode from the point of view of 19th century Brazilian medical research. Particular attention will be drawn to the work of João Batista de Lacerda (1846-1915), who claimed the discovery of a microorganism (*Bacillus beribericus*) which he identified as the cause of beriberi.³

2. INCIDENCE OF BERIBERI IN BRAZIL IN THE LATE 19TH CENTURY

Beriberi is a disease that was known in the East from the earliest times. It became known to European medicine shortly after the period of the Iberian discoveries. It was described by the Portuguese chronicler Diogo do Couto. He pointed out its incidence among the sailors of Gonçalo Pereira's fleet, in India: "Our people became ill because of a disease they call berebere, that is a swelling of the belly, and of the legs, from which they die in a few days, as many have died, and on some days ten, and twelve" (Couto, 1736-1737, vol. 3, p. 389).

Fig. 1. "O Lavrador de Café" (The coffee worker), 1939, Cândido Portinari (MASP, São Paulo, Brazil).
Photograph by Paulisson Miura (Creative Commons Attribution 2.0 Generic license).

In Brazil, this sickness was called "the swelling of legs", or "the swollen legs pestilence" (Almeida, 1916 p. 10), because of one of its symptoms. Cândido Portinari, the famous Brazilian artist, depicted in several of his paintings human figures that present the likeness of beriberi

² The word "vitamin" was created in 1912, by Casimir Funk. For a general view of the discovery of vitamins, see Sharman (1977).

³ This paper was written in 1996, on the occasion of the researches that resulted in the publication of our book on the history of contagious diseases (Martins et al., 1997).

patients (Fig. 1). Besides this visible symptom (that sometimes is absent, however), there is a general weakness, reduced sensibility of the limbs, difficulty of locomotion (that sometimes turns into paralysis), and a peculiar feeling of strong pressure around the waist, like a tightened belt (*epigastric girdle*). Asphyxia and death may occur in serious cases (Silva Lima, 1872, p. 78).

The incidence of beriberi increased in the 19th century, when polished (white) rice became common in Asia. Nowadays we know that polishing the rice deprives it of B vitamin. Towards the middle of the 19th century, exportation of white rice from Asia reached the whole world. For that reason, in the second half of the 19th century beriberi spread and became common also in Brazil (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, p. 859).

In 1858, there occurred a “swollen legs epidemic” in a religious school in Mariana (Minas Gerais). Several children were killed by the disease (Almeida, 1916 p. 18). Many cases occur in the 1860’s, at different places. In Mato Grosso, military forces were attained by the disease. Soldiers tried to escape from death running away from the “plague”. At about the same time, beriberi also arose in Bahia.

The first Brazilian medical papers on beriberi were published in 1867 by José Zepherino de Menezes Brum (1825-1893) and by José Francisco de Silva Lima (1826-1910) (Costa, p. 308). A comprehensive catalogue of Brazilian medical books and papers (*Catalogo da exposição medica brasileira*), published in 1884, allows us to follow the rise of studies on beriberi that occurred in the late 19th century. Over 60 works were published between 1871 and 1880 (Costa, 1884, pp. 314-316).

José Francisco da Silva Lima was one of the first Brazilian physicians to study the disease⁴. He described 51 events, with 38 deaths. He believed that beriberi was not a transmissible illness:

Without assuming any theory about this matter, that is, without leaving the realm of facts, I will say that the disease did not seem to spread by contagion or infection; it did seem to depend on a widely disseminated morbid cause, on unknown general hygienic conditions or circumstances. (Silva Lima, 1872, p. 76)

To avoid the disease, Silva Lima recommended personal hygiene, wines, healthy food, change of airs, salt baths. In case of illness, treatment included quinine, iron prescriptions, and diuretic, purgative or emetic medicines. Silva Lima conjectured that beriberi was related to food and compared it to ergotism – a disease produced by a cereal fungus. However, he did not reach any definite conclusion about its cause: he suggested that there could be influences of the weather, marshland miasmas, impure waters, etc.

At this time, before the general acceptance of the microbial theory of diseases, beriberi received several different explanations all over the world (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, pp. 863-6). In the 1870s it was compared to rheumatism, since both diseases increased in rainy weather. It was also associated to anæmia and to paludism. It was found more frequently in places close to rivers or to the sea. It was also suggested that it could be produced by some microorganism found in fish, as beriberi was very common among people from the Far East who fed on raw fish. Sometimes it was explained as due to parasites, since intestinal worms were found in some beriberi victims.

The disease often occurred in prisons, hospitals, shelters and ships, affecting several people at the same time (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, p. 865). This suggested that it could be a contagious illness.

⁴ Silva Lima published his first studies as a series of short articles that appeared from 1867 onwards in the journal *Gazeta Médica da Bahia*. His book on the subject was published in 1872.

In 1871, a serious beriberi epidemic brought death to many inmates of the *Casa de Detenção* (prison), in Recife (Almeida, 1916, p. 20).

At the Caraça religious boarding school (Minas Gerais), there were beriberi epidemics from 1861 to 1911. In 1873, 45 of the 230 children were attained by the disease – 12 of them with paralysis, with 2 deaths. In the first epidemics, a medical committee ascribed the disease to the nitre added by the priests to the water drank by the students with the intent of decreasing their sexual desires. Later, another medical committee explained the occurrence of beriberi as due to the air moisture, to the large number of children in a small place, and to rotten rice (Almeida, 1916, p. 78-79).

Beriberi also became common among the inhabitants of Rio de Janeiro (Table 1). Towards the turn of the century, only four diseases produced a larger number of deaths than beriberi in that city: tuberculosis, smallpox, malaria and influenza. Casualties due to typhus, measles and dysentery were fewer than those due to beriberi.

Table 1. Beriberi casualties in Rio de Janeiro (Almeida, 1916, p. 67)

Year:	Number of deaths:
1885	36
1886	67
1887	64
1888	61
1889	448
1890	332
1891	156
1892	191
1893	81
1894	363
1895	128
1896	273
1897	302
1898	276
1899	149
1900	152

3. BERIBERI IN THE BRAZILIAN NAVY

In the Brazilian Navy, beriberi became an increasingly serious problem. In 1875, there occurred 19 cases of illness among sailors in Bahia. In the next year, the disease affected 39 people. In 1883, beriberi impacted 111 sailors in a single ship (“Niterói”) during its trip to Bahia (Almeida, 1916, p. 81).

A tragic and famous occurrence of beriberi took place during the circumnavigation voyage of the Brazilian Navy ship “Vital de Oliveira”, from the end of 1879 to the beginning of 1881. The medical aspects of the trip were described by Galdino Cícero de Magalhães (1848-1911), the physician who accompanied the tour (Magalhães, 1882).

The ship left Rio de Janeiro on the 19th November 1879 and headed towards Portugal. It arrived to Lisbon and then traversed the Mediterranean sea. The ship reached the Suez Canal in the beginning of April 1880. One month later, it arrived to Ceylon (Sri Lanka) and health problems were observed: swellings and tonsillitis.

Magalhães described the occurrence of heavy rains and high temperature at this time. He ascribed the health problems to “a miasmatic infection originating at the ship storage, from which,

during the whole travel, there came a fetid smell due to grease rotten in the lower parts of the ship” (Magalhães, 1882, p. 13).

Two cases were diagnosed as beriberi at that time. Two new cases occurred towards the end of May, after arriving to Hong Kong. The physician associated the disease to the high temperature and humidity. He treated the patients with quinine, sodium arsenate, tonics, warm baths, Fioravanti oil massages, purgatives and other medicines. The health of two of the sailors improved, but the other two exhibited no recovery. They exhibited swollen legs, weakness and difficulty of locomotion, muscular pain, vomit, epigastric girdle. Magalhães changed the treatment, using a large spectrum of medicines: iron arsenate, arsenious acid, strychnine sulphate, phosphoric acid, digitalis, aconite, quinine wine and even electric shocks. “By the use of those means, the symptoms exhibited a sensible decrease of their energy” (Magalhães, 1882, p. 14).

It is likely that, during this part of the travel, as the ship arrived to different ports in China and Japan, the food had been changed and its content was more satisfactory, producing the observed improvement. However, from July to the end of August, the ship sailed through the Pacific Ocean to California – without fresh food, of course. Health problems increased, and in August there were 29 beriberi patients. Three sailors died. Medications produced no improvement and the physician explained the fact as due to constant heat, rains and humidity. Besides, he remarked that the food was poor: they had no fresh vegetables – only salted meat and rice (Magalhães, 1882, p. 26). At last, the ship arrived to San Francisco, where 18 sailors were admitted to the hospital – four of them died.

Magalhães concluded that beriberi was due to toxic blood produced by high temperature, moistness, poor nourishment, large number of people in a small place, sorrow, weariness (Magalhães, 1882, p. 43). The physician recommended the following change in the ship diet: use of potatoes, canned and dry vegetables, use of pepper and other spices, and alcoholic drinks at meals (Magalhães, 1882, p. 52-53).

Beriberi persisted as a serious health problem in the Brazilian Navy. At the beginning of 1889, beriberi became the most important cause of disease, and the Navy Minister summoned the Navy Health Committee (*Junta de Saúde da Armada*) to study the measures to be applied to fight beriberi. The Committee consisted of Carlos Frederico dos Santos Xavier e Azevedo (the Committee reporter), Bento de Carvalho e Souza, Barão de Ribeiro de Almeida and José Caetano da Costa (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, p. 3). Several questions were addressed to the Committee, including this: “4. Whether the propagation of the disease in the Navy is due to contagion or to specific changes of our weather and land that indistinctly assault the urban and marine people, or to peculiar circumstances of our ships and quarters, or to some hazardous diet of the crew” (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, p. 4). The question itself suggested the popular explanations of beriberi of that time, including the one we nowadays believe to be correct – wrong diet.

There was at that time a special infirmary for beriberi patients at the island of Bom Jesus, in Rio de Janeiro. It was observed that the health of the sailors treated in that infirmary did seldom improve. On the other side, patients moved to a hospital in Nova Friburgo were soon healed. This led to the comparison of both places. In Bom Jesus there were beaches (where rotten marine plants and animals could be found) and marshes; it was close to Sapucaia, the place where the city refuse was burned, bringing to the infirmary its bad smell (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, pp. 4-5). According to the miasma theory of diseases, it was a very unhealthy place. On the other hand, Nova Friburgo was far from the sea, on the mountains, with no marshes. Its climate was mild and the hydrotherapy used there, with strong warm or cold douches, was supposed to stimulate the nervous system (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, pp. 5-7).

The members of the Committee disagreed about the cause of beriberi. Some of them accepted that the disease depended on climate, land and other infecting conditions; but it seemed

that it was also contagious (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, pp. 7-8). The high incidence of the disease in the Navy pointed out that there were specific causes (perhaps of hygienic nature) acting on the ships and accommodations. According to those beliefs, the Committee recommended 19 measures that could be instrumental in the reduction of beriberi in the Navy (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, pp. 9-10). They included frequent cleaning and disinfection of the ships, avoidance of heavy work, change of clothes when they became wet, diversity of food, etc.

The President of the Committee disagreed with the other members concerning several points (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, pp. 11-18). He did not accept that the illness was contagious. He partly accepted the presence of microorganisms in beriberi, but wondered whether they were cause or effect of the disease. He stressed that the infectious germ was present in ships and quarters that did not respect hygienic principles. He also accepted that malnutrition (specially lack of protein) contributed to the appearance of beriberi and suggested that physicians should pay attention to food (Xavier e Azevedo, 1889, p. 18).

The recommendations of the Committee produced no improvement in the condition of the Navy. From 1890 to 1896, there were 1,266 beriberi marine patients in Rio de Janeiro, with 112 deaths (Almeida, 1916, p. 81).

4. LACERDA'S DISCOVERY OF BACILLUS BERIBERICUS

It was just natural that beriberi became the subject of several studies in Brazil, at the end of the 19th century. From the 1880s onwards, hypotheses about microorganisms as cause of beriberi became common (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, pp. 869-74). All over the world, several researchers have also allegedly found the microbial cause of beriberi (Vedder, 1913, p. 128).

Quite a few Brazilian physicians found microorganisms in beriberi patients. The earlier experimental investigation was developed by Antônio Pacífico Pereira (1846-1922), who found some microscopic round bodies in the blood of diseased people in Bahia; his work will be mentioned later, because he criticized Lacerda. Augusto Maia found a kind of micrococcus; Paulo Mendes observed some germs in the marrow vessels; Francisco Fajardo detected a hematozoon similar to that of malaria in beriberi patients; and as late as 1911, Lydio Parahyba presented a thesis on a supposed beriberi coccus (Fajardo, 1898, p. 5; Almeida, 1916, pp. 21-22).

João Batista de Lacerda was, however, the best known Brazilian defender of the microbial explanation of beriberi, from 1883 to his death. It may seem pathetic to find a microorganism that does not exist; it is, however, highly instructive to scrutinize Lacerda's works, in order to understand the difficulties of an adequate use of the microbial theory of diseases.

Fig. 2. João Baptista de Lacerda

4.1 Lacerda's career

João Batista de Lacerda (1846-1915) was a Brazilian physician (Fig. 2). He obtained his Medicine degree in 1870. After some years working as a physician, he was appointed in 1876 as vice-director of the First Section (Anthropology, Zoology and Paleontology) of the National Museum (*Museu Nacional*), in Rio de Janeiro. In 1880 he was appointed vice-director of the Laboratory of Experimental Physiology of the Museum⁵. Afterwards, Lacerda became the director of the First Section and of the Laboratory. From 1895 to his death, Lacerda was the General Director of the Museum.

Between 1877 and 1881 Lacerda published a series of anthropological and paleontological studies. At the same time he began the publication of a succession of studies on poisons (specially those of snakes). In 1881, he reported that potassium permanganate was useful as an antidote of snake poison – a discovery that was contested and led to the first scientific controversy of Lacerda's career. From 1883 onwards he published researches on yellow fever and beriberi. In both cases, he claimed the discovery of pathogenic microorganisms that caused those diseases⁶. He is also known for his controversial defense of the need of “whitening” the Brazilian population.

4.2 Lacerda's method

Lacerda's point of departure in the study of beriberi was, of course, the microbiological works of Pasteur and Koch (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 12-13). He seemed well aware of the excesses

⁵ For biographical information on Lacerda, see: Blake, 1883-1902, vol. 3, pp. 342-347; Silva & Aranha, 1858-1923, vol. 10, pp. 174-175; vol. 11, p. 277; Velho Sobrinho, 1937-1940, vol. 2, pp. 178-183.

⁶ In 1880, Domingos José Freire Jr. (1842-1899) claimed the discovery of a *Cryptococcus xantogenicus* that was supposed to produce yellow fever. In 1883, Lacerda ascribed that disease to another microorganism that he called *Fungus febris flavæ*. Both works have not been confirmed by other researchers (Franco, 1969, p. 47).

of ascribing all diseases to microscopic parasites and criticized hurried conclusions (Lacerda, 1883, p. 15). Lacerda accepted, however, that every disease where contagion or transmission is observed, such as yellow fever, cholera, typhus, bubonic plague, smallpox, scarlet fever, rabies, etc., were due to microscopic causes (Lacerda, 1883, p. 15).

According to Robert Koch, a microscopic parasite could be accepted as the cause of a disease if and only if:

Firstly, that the parasite is found in every single case of the disease in question, and under conditions corresponding to the pathological changes and to the clinical course of the disease;

Secondly, that it occurs in no other disease as an accidental and non-pathogenic parasite;

Thirdly, that when isolated from the body and propagated through a sufficient number of pure cultivations, it can produce the disease anew;

The microbe under these circumstances cannot be an accidental accompaniment of the disease, and no other relationship between the parasite and the disease can be conceived, except that the former is the cause of the latter. (Koch, 1890, pp. 11-12)

There were several difficulties in applying this method, as pointed out by Koch himself. First, it was necessary to identify a specific kind of corpuscles, distinguishing it from any other bodily constituents; it was then necessary to prove that they were living beings, with spontaneous motion, growth and reproduction; it was necessary to distinguish that microorganism from other microbes; it was necessary to separate it from all other substances and corpuscles contained in an organism attained by the disease; it was necessary to produce exactly the same disease (with the same symptoms and evolution) in healthy organisms by the sole introduction of the microscopic parasites (Koch, 1890, pp. 3-4; see also Koch, in Dolan & Adams-Smith, 1978, pp. 144-147). Each of those steps is full of pitfalls.

Lacerda was aware of the difficulties and tried to follow the best experimental methods. In his second publication, he explicitly described Koch's postulates (Lacerda, 1887, p. 46). Lacerda studied the blood of several beriberi patients and found some peculiar microorganisms. In order to check whether they were the cause of the disease, he tried to follow Koch's principles, cultivating them outside the sick organism. Afterwards, he attempted to produce the disease by inoculation of the microorganism.

He declared that he had learned Pasteur's method from Jean-Claude Rebourgeon, a veterinary surgeon who had attended Pasteur's laboratory in Paris (Lacerda, 1883, p. 19).⁷

4.3 Preparation of the culture medium

The nutrient medium chosen by Lacerda was cow meat stock. After due cooking, the infusion was filtered twice and placed in glass vessels that were closed by fire. The vessels were afterwards put for some time in an oven kept at 130 to 140 Celsius. Kept for a few days at room temperature, the stock continued transparent and clean, without development of microorganisms, showing that sterilization had succeeded (Lacerda, 1883, p. 21).

4.4 Blood collection and examination

The blood of five beriberi patients was collected into sterilized glass tubes (Lacerda, 1883, p. 20). Details about the collection procedure were published in Lacerda's second work. He washed one finger of the sick person with soap or alcohol. The finger was then pressed and pricked with a pin that had been previously passed through a flame. The blood drop arising from the puncture was then aspirated through a capillary glass tube that had been sterilized at 180 degrees. When the tube was full, its ends were closed with sealing wax. Several tubes were

⁷ Jean-Claude Rebourgeon arrived to Brazil in 1883, hired by the Brazilian government to implement the production of smallpox vaccine.

filled with the blood of each patient. A small drop was also collected and put between two glass slides for immediate examination.

In all cases, Lacerda observed, interspersed with the blood globules, some very small bright corpuscles with spherical or egg-like shape, that exhibited fast translational and rotational movements. He stated that they were, doubtless, some kind of living micrococcus. In some cases the corpuscle grew in one direction, then it became narrower at the central region and formed a diplococcus (Lacerda, 1887, p. 51-52).

The most common form he observed was that of long filaments, some of them attaining 10 to 15 micra (Lacerda, 1887, p. 54). He stated that those threads, in the germination phase, became filled with small egg-shaped corpuscles, with the size of 2 to 3 micra, that afterwards are released (*ibid.*, p. 55). According to Lacerda, those microorganisms could take several different forms, such as that of a bacillus, or a streptococcus, or a diplococcus.

4.5 Culture of the microorganism

The external walls of the tubes containing blood of beriberi patients were washed in phenic acid and water. With the aid of tweezers they were broken and dropped into the glass vessel containing the nutrient medium. Those vessels were closed and brought to a stove, where they were kept at 37 degrees. Lacerda reported that he soon observed the emergence of white flakes in the liquid (Lacerda, 1887, p. 52).

Fig. 3. Lacerda's drawings of *Bacillus beribericus*, after 20 hours of culture (left) and after three days (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 23, 26).

Lacerda's first work shows the evolution of those cultures: he observed long strings with interspersed corpuscles (Fig. 3). Afterwards, some of those strings broke into smaller pieces, forming bacteria. He also observed corpuscles around those pieces, which were interpreted as spores. He called his microorganism *Bacillus beribericus* (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 23-27). According to Lacerda, the new microorganism was similar to *Bacillus anthracis*, as he recognized from Émile Duclaux publications and from a preparation that had been brought from Paris by Rebourgeon (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 25-26). Similar bacteria were also observed in urine cultures (*ibid.*, p. 30).

4.6 Inoculation of the culture

The next step was to produce the disease in healthy organisms by inoculating the culture. Lacerda tried the experiment with Guinea pigs and rabbits with seemingly success.

On the 3rd August 1883, Lacerda inoculated the thighs of three Guinea pigs. One of them soon died, and its blood was full of bacteria. Lacerda used the blood of the dead animal to inoculate other Guinea pigs, and all of them died. The experiment was repeated and succeeded with other Guinea pigs. Lacerda described the presence of *Bacillus beribericus* in all of them (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 34-35). However, he observed no symptom related to beriberi (such as paralysis).

Fig. 4. Lacerda's drawings of *Bacillus beribericus*, found in the marrow (left) and in muscles (right) of infected animals (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 40, 47)

Two rabbits were inoculated with half cubic centimetre of the culture. One of them died after five days and its blood and tissues contained the *Bacillus beribericus* (Fig. 4). The other rabbit died after 19 days. Lacerda reported anomalous locomotion. Similar effects were observed in a second trial with two rabbits. Both died after a few days, and Lacerda noticed that they had some difficulty in moving their hind legs. He also described that they exhibited analgesia (Lacerda, 1883, pp. 37-44).

In Lacerda's opinion, those tests concluded the proof that he had detected the microscopic cause of beriberi.

4.7 The finding of *Bacillus beribericus* in moulded rice

In the decade of 1880, the role of vitamins had not been established. However, there was a suspicion that beriberi was somehow related to rice, as that disease was more common among the rice eating eastern people (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, pp. 875-6). In Brazil, this conjecture was suggested in 1873 by Augusto Cezar Miranda de Azevedo (Almeida, 1916, p. 113) but it led to no detailed research.

Fig. 5. Lacerda's drawing of *Bacillus beribericus* found in rice (Lacerda, 1883, p. 61).

Lacerda received information about an isolated case of beriberi: the patient had no contact with any other ill person. He suspected that the disease could have been transmitted by food. He studied the rice consumed by that patient and noticed that some of the grains were brittle, dull, and they turned into powder when they were pressed. In their surface, Lacerda detected a microscopic parasite (Fig. 5): small strings similar to those observed in the cultures of the blood from beriberi patients (Lacerda, 1883, p. 57).

Lacerda cultivated the rice microorganism in cow meat stock and observed corpuscles and bacteria similar to those arising from infected blood. Was it really the *Bacillus beribericus*? In order to check this conjecture, Lacerda fed the moulded rice to a female mouse. After six days, the little animal miscarried four fetuses. Two days later, Lacerda observed that the fingers of one of its legs were red and swollen. On the 12th day, the mouse died exhibiting asphyxia and convulsions. Its blood contained corpuscles similar to those of beriberi patients, and the culture of this blood reproduced “all the forms of the *Bacillus beribericus*” (Lacerda, 1883, p. 60-61). Hence, he concluded that rice could carry the microorganism that produced beriberi. This was a vindication of Silva Lima’s suggestion that beriberi was similar to ergotism.

4.8 What could be wrong in Lacerda’s work?

Lacerda was apparently following Koch’s method. According to his description, he first observed that the microorganism was found in the blood of all beriberi patients; he then cultivated the microorganism; he produced the disease in healthy animals, by inoculation of the culture; the animals became sick; and he observed the same microorganism in those animals. What could be wrong?

There are several doubtful aspects in Lacerda’s research. There were corpuscles in the blood of beriberi patients – but were they microscopic living beings? Lacerda described their motion and division, but it could happen that he saw what he wanted to observe.

If there was, indeed, a microorganism in the blood of beriberi patients, was it really associated to beriberi, or was it due to a secondary infection? Could similar microorganisms be found in healthy people or in people attained by different diseases? Lacerda did not discuss those possibilities – nor did he test them.

Did Lacerda really identify a definite kind of microorganism, or did he observe several different kinds of corpuscles and – for lack of training – supposed that all of them corresponded to the same kind of organism? Sometimes, Lacerda describes his microorganism as assuming different forms – therefore, it is likely that he observed several different microbes. For untrained eyes, all bacteria are alike – as all dark birds look equal to the eyes of a small child. It would be necessary to identify Lacerda’s *Bacillus beribericus* by specific features or reactions – such as those developed by Koch in his researches.

Was the microorganism observed in his cultures the same microorganism observed in the blood of beriberi patients? Probably not. It is likely that the culture medium was contaminated by airborne microbes, during manipulation of the vessels. Lacerda never attempted control experiments with healthy blood or with the blood taken from patients with other diseases. It is likely that he would have observed similar bacteria in his culture if he had made those tests.

Did the animals inoculated with Lacerda’s culture really acquire beriberi? Of course, they acquired *some* disease – but how could Lacerda recognize beriberi in animals that had never been observed to exhibit beriberi? Again, it would be necessary to identify some specific features of beriberi in all animals; it would be necessary to inoculate them with different cultures and with blood from patients with different diseases, in order to compare their effects.

Koch’s method is not as straightforward as it might seem. Its use is full of delicate aspects.

5. ROCHARD’S CRITICISM OF LACERDA’S RESULTS

Lacerda’s research was strongly criticized, both by Brazilian physicians and by foreign ones.

Soon after the publication of his first work, Lacerda has sent his memoir to Henri-Marie Bouley (1814-1885), a professor of surgical pathology at the École Nationale Vétérinaire d'Alfort, asking him to present the work to the Paris Academy of Medicine. Bouley was a strong enthusiast of Louis Pasteur’s microbiological researches. He was acquainted with Lacerda because of his researches on snake poisoning.

After receiving the booklet, Bouley offered it to the Academy of Medicine, on 15 January 1884.⁸ He suggested that dr. Rochard could present a report on that research, and the suggestion was accepted by the Academy.

Jules Eugène Rochard (1819-1896), a member of the French Academy of Medicine, was at that time the general superintendent of the health service of the French Navy. He was well acquainted with the so-called “tropical diseases”, including beriberi. Notwithstanding the circumstance that Lacerda’s booklet had been published only in Portuguese, he accepted the charge, and two weeks later he presented a report on Lacerda’s work (Rochard, 1884). He remarked that beriberi was a mysterious disease:

This disease offers another kind of interest. It is a real pathological enigma. I believe I have read everything of importance that has been written about it. This is a question that I have often had to deal with, and I am forced to admit that I am no further ahead than before having studied it. Its cause, above all, has hitherto seemed to elude all investigation. (Rochard, 1884, p. 176)

The first part of the report (Rochard, 1884, pp. 176-183) is a detailed and faithful description of Lacerda’s experiments and conclusions. After this presentation, he remarked:

Here, Gentlemen, is the faithful translation of M. de Lacerda’s pamphlet and the sincere summary of his experiences. I have put this translation in front of M. Pasteur. He took the trouble to read it and told me that this research had been well conducted and that it showed the author’s practice of this kind of work. He has not, of course, expressed any opinion on the results that he has not been able to control and I will certainly not be more daring, I who do not have the slightest authority in such matters. However, I believe it is my duty to present some reservations and to express to the Academy the doubts which the reading of this work has left on me. (Rochard, 1884, p. 183)

Rochard commented that the experiments were always successful, and that this was quite unusual: “Those lucky experimental results, so numerous and so complete, are suspicious to me” (Rochard, 1884, p. 184).

Does this mean that I suspect the good faith of M. de Lacerda? Not at all. His work bears the imprint of sincerity; but it is not people of bad faith who are to be feared in the scientific world, but men of imagination, enthusiasts. Their scientific ardor puts before their eyes a prism through which they see everything they want to discover. (Rochard, 1884, p. 184)

Rochard recalled some recent failures of Lacerda, in several researches: (1) In 1878 he reported the discovery of a yeast that was the cause of the effects of snake venom; (2) In 1881, he claimed that potasse permanganate was an antidote for snake poison; (3) In 1883, he maintained that he had found a microscopic fungus that was the cause of yellow fever (Rochard, 1884, pp. 184-185). None of those claims was confirmed by other researchers.

Jules Rochard remarked that Lacerda did not refer to previous researchers who had examined the blood of people with beriberi, and then he pointed out that observations had been made in India, the United States, and Brazil (Rochard, 1884, pp. 185-186).

None of these observers saw anything similar to this branched bacillus, arranged in a bush or a reed and so abundant, that it is difficult to explain that it could have escaped the eyes of so many people, especially when one thinks that Pacifico Pereira used magnifications from 12 to 1500 diameters. (Rochard, 1884, p. 186)

⁸ Notice published in *L’Union Médicale*, 37: 104, 1884: “M. Bouley dépose, au nome de M. Lacerda, un *Mémoire sur la découverte du microbe du béri-béri.*”

There were other problems pointed out by Jules Rochard. Lacerda had asserted that the spores of his microbe only resisted to temperatures up to 90 degrees.⁹ Rochard remarked that rice is eaten only after been cooked for a long time; therefore, Lacerda's rice microorganisms could never produce any disease, in contradiction with the supposition of the Brazilian researcher (Rochard, 1884, p. 188). At the end of his report, he presented the need of an independent and authoritative confirmation of Lacerda's results, before they could be accepted:

Summing up, I repeat that I do not distrust either the good faith or the talent of M. de Lacerda; but the results which he announced are too surprising to be admitted before they have been checked. This control could not be easier. M. de Lacerda has only to send M. Pasteur some tubes containing the blood of patients and animals on which he has made his experiments, and our learned colleague will hasten to repeat them. He has assured me of it and, if he obtains results similar to those of M. de Lacerda, we will only have to bow our heads. (Rochard, 1884, p. 188)

Lacerda never provided the required samples to Pasteur.

The report presented by Jules Rochard to the Medicine Academy had strong impact. Short accounts were published in several journals. Lacerda soon became aware of the report through one of those indirect sources and he immediately replied, publishing an article written in French, in the Brazilian journal *União Médica* (Lacerda, 1884).

In his reply, Lacerda first pointed out that Jules Rochard was only acquainted with medical clinic and that he had never developed laboratory experiments, being therefore unskilled in the subject (Lacerda, 1884b, p. 185). He conceded that he had only have knowledge of the report through a synopsis published in the newspaper *Le Temps*, but nevertheless he attempted to criticize Rochard's account. According to Lacerda, the report contained no argument against his research, it only presented Rochard's personal reaction:

“What! Is it possible that beriberi, which I consider to be a pathological problem, is produced by a microphyte and that this microphyte is found in the rice?” This simple mental question created the whole situation, in which the illustrious Mr. Rochard had the good part. (Lacerda, 1884b, p. 187)

Lacerda insinuated that Rochard belonged to the group of those who did not accept the microbe theory of diseases, and he stated that, instead of presenting arguments against his work on beriberi, the French doctor only attacked his old researches, presenting him as “a deluded man” (Lacerda, 1884b, p. 188). Accordingly, instead of defending his study of beriberi, Lacerda argued for his previous researches on the microbe he had found in snake venom, the use of potassium permanganate as an antidote against this poisson, and the alleged discovery of the microorganism that produced yellow fever. One could expect that Lacerda would present a more detailed defense of his work after he read the full version of Rochard's statement; however, Lacerda never published any other rejoinder to the report.

A few months later, the physician João Paulo de Carvalho (1854-1905), who taught Physiology at the Medicine School of Rio de Janeiro, recalled Rochard's negative report¹⁰ and he commented:

These studies, carried out in such a haste, and without a rigorous method, bring great discredit to Brazil's scientific reputation in Europe, a reputation for which we must be all the

⁹ “Do not eat rice except after exposing it to prolonged cooking, since the parasite's spores resist to a temperature of up to 90° C” (Lacerda, 1883, p. 66).

¹⁰ In his public talk, which was attended by the Brazilian emperor Pedro II, Carvalho criticized both Lacerda and Domingos José Freire Junior (1842-1899), who claimed the discovery of the *Micrococcus xanthogenicus*, that allegedly produced yellow fever.

more zealous, as we are just beginning to attract the attention of the wise men of the old world. (Carvalho, 1884, pp. 47-48)

6. PACIFICO PEREIRA'S CRITICISM

Lacerda's research on beriberi was criticized, in Brazil, by the physician Antonio Pacífico Pereira (1846-1922). Pacífico Pereira was full professor of Anatomy of the School of Medicine of Bahia. He was a well known authority on beriberi, at that time. He had recently published a long series of papers on the subject (Pereira, 1881-1882), where he reported – among other things – his own microscopical analysis of the blood of people who had this disease. In 1883, before finishing his researches, Lacerda had already made known his main conclusions by notices published in newspapers. In October 1883, Pacífico Pereira published a comment on those researchs, where he summarized the information about Lacerda's work that was available at the time, and he commented:

The discovery of a microbe in the blood of beriberians is not a novelty in science, nor are new the experiments carried out with the culture of the blood of individuals affected by this disease. In several articles published in this *Gazette* [*Gazeta Medica da Bahia*] in 1881 on the etiology and nature of beriberi, which the *União Medica* of Rio de Janeiro did us the honor of duplicating, we have dealt with the hematology of beriberi and described the microorganism that we have often seen and studied in the blood of individuals affected by this disease. (Pereira, 1883, pp. 161-162)

Notice that Lacerda did not refer to those previous researches by Pacífico Pereira, as Rochard remarked in his report.

In the next pages of his article, Pacífico Pereira reproduced several parts of the papers he had published two years before. In those extracts he described the observation of small corpuscles in the blood of beriberi patients, their form, size, and motion. He also gave an account of experiments he made of cultures with those corpuscles, their reproduction, and trials of inoculation in dogs of the liquid containing the microorganism. The outcome of those tests was negative – the dogs did not acquire any illness, and the microorganism was not found in their blood. The author did not conclude that those microbes were the cause of beriberi, and he suggested several specific topics that should be investigated to ascertain whether they really produce beriberi or not:

There is still a long way that must be overtook to reach this conclusion, and it is convenient to study the following topics in Rio de Janeiro, as we have been trying to do here:

1. Whether these microbes exist only in the blood of patients with beriberi;
2. If they are present there only as spores, or in another state of evolution;
3. To isolate completely these microbes of the blood of patients with beriberi, from all other foreign microorganisms, to reproduce them by culture, and to inoculate them in different animals, with their identity being fully demonstrated;
4. To show that the symptoms presented by the inoculated animals correspond in their characteristic features to the clinical delineation of beriberi;
5. To demonstrate that the lesions observed in animals that succumb to inoculation are identical to the anatomo-pathological alterations demonstrated in the autopsy of individuals who died from beriberi.

It is premature to draw a definitive conclusion before these premises are fully demonstrated.

For our part, we frankly declare, we cannot yet reach this conclusion; after nearly two years of continuous study, we decided to expect new facts and, especially, more autopsies. (Pereira, 1883, p. 166)

Notice that Pacífico Pereira was very careful concerning the method that should be followed, and that he did not draw any hasty conclusion.

Towards the end of his paper, the author pointed out some discrepancies between Lacerda's results and his own findings:

From his succinct communication [...] we see that there is a notable difference between the description of the microorganisms he observed, and those that we have always observed here in the blood of the beriberians, and we suspect that some element extraneous to the disease we have been studying has developed in the cultures made by the distinguished colleague. [...]

We also add that we have never found, in the blood of beriberians, microorganisms with the morphological qualities that make them similar to the anthrax bacteria; that the micrococci we have found in the blood of beriberians also exist in the blood of other individuals not attacked by this disease; and, finally, that the injuries found by Mr. Dr. Lacerda in the autopsy of the animals that succumbed to the inoculation of the product of cultures of the mentioned microorganisms do not correspond to those that we have found in the anatomo-pathological exams of the individuals who died of beriberi. (Pereira, 1883, p. 170)

A few months later, after his memoir had been published, Lacerda replied to this article (Lacerda, 1884a). He attempted to show that his work was completely new, different from the researches of Pacífico Pereira:

[...] I hope I can demonstrate, without offending the delicacy and susceptibilities of my colleague, that nothing in common exists, neither concerning the methods employed in the investigation, nor in the results obtained, between my work and those of dr. Pacífico about the cause of beriberi. (Lacerda, 1884a, p. 115)

Lacerda suggested that the sterilization process used by Pacífico Pereira was faulty, and that he did not keep the cultures in a stove, at a constant temperature – therefore, their experiments were different and their results cannot be compared. Besides that, Lacerda claimed that the bacilli he observed was completely different from Pereira's micrococci and, therefore, what he found was new (Lacerda, 1884a, pp. 115-116). Lacerda misinterpreted Pacífico Pereira's claim, stating that he wrongly alleged the discovery of the same microorganism, several years before. As a matter of fact, Pacífico Pereira never declared that.

7. LACERDA AND PEKELHARING

In 1887, Lacerda published a new book, with fuller details of his research on beriberi. None of the difficulties pointed out above were discussed or circumvented in that work, however. He commented that he had submitted an improved version of his memoir to the Imperial Academy of Medicine of Rio de Janeiro. A committee was formed to study Lacerda's research but, for some unknown reason, it never presented a report (Lacerda, 1887, pp. 48-49).

The first part of this work presents a review of the disease and the main hypotheses that had been proposed to explain it: the weather (heat and humidity); influence from the marshes; and nourishment – unvarying food, of insufficient amount and unhealthy. He criticized each of those hypothesis, and particularly the one that was closer to the truth, according to our current knowledge:

The production of beriberi by very uniform food, insufficient and of poor quality is nonsense, as this disease has grown among us, on a large scale, under the influence of entirely different dietary conditions. To accommodate the facts to his etiological theory, which considers the

beriberi produced by a *defective nutrition*, Férís¹¹ says that the meat used as public food in Brazil is little and of poor quality – and that is not true. If by *defective nutrition* we must understand insufficient food of poor quality, one should ask Mr. Férís whether that is not the case for the food in some rural districts of Europe and among the indigent classes of the manufacturing cities of France and England. And why this disease does not arise in those countries, if that is the cause of beriberi, in Mr. Férís' opinion? (Lacerda, 1887, pp. 41-42)

After dismissing the usual hypotheses, Lacerda offered a detailed description of his own researches, and he declared that several researchers had recently confirmed his conclusions: Ogata Masanori and Wallace Taylor in Japan, F. J. Cornelissen e J. Sugenoja in the Dutch India (Lacerda, 1887, p. 136). As a matter of fact, all those researchers – and several others – reported the discovery of different beriberi microorganisms.

Was Lacerda's work regarded as clearly wrong, at that time? No, it was not. Any careful researcher could detect some gaps in his method, but maybe he had observed the correct microorganisms.

In 1886, the physician Cornelis Adrianus Pekelharing (1848-1922) and his assistant Cornelis Winkler were sent from Utrecht to India by the Dutch government to study beriberi and to propose procedures to fight that disease (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, pp. 876-877; Erdman, 1964). Pekelharing was aware of Lacerda's research; before his travel, and he asked him to send copies of his works. Lacerda replied and sent to him his papers. At the same time, he requested Pekelharing to inform him about the development of his researches in India. Pekelharing kept Lacerda informed, but his reports were written in Dutch. With the help of the Dutch consul in Rio de Janeiro (Mr. F. Palm), Lacerda translated and afterwards published Pekelharing's reports (Pekelharing, 1889). According to Lacerda, there was a complete accord between Pekelharing's and his own conclusions: the cause of beriberi had been found (Lacerda, in Pekelharing, 1889, p. 4).

The agreement between Lacerda's and Pekelharing's findings was not complete, however. Pekelharing did observe microorganisms in the blood of beriberi patients, but the ones he saw were not the same that had been described by Lacerda. Pekelharing found corpuscles (micrococci) and sticks (bacteria), but they were smaller than those described by Lacerda. They were also smaller than those described by other previous researchers (Pekelharing, 1889, p. 15).

This circumstance throws some light on the difficulty of the investigation, at that time. Only a handful of researchers at that time were able to recognize different microorganisms, to describe their peculiarities, to check their reactions to different dyes, etc. In most cases, the technique was crude, with low power microscopes, with no precise identification, with no dyes. In those circumstances, it was natural that different investigators isolated different organisms (Scott, 1939, vol. 2, p. 870).

Pekelharing's method was similar to that of Lacerda. In his first report, Pekelharing described that the number of bacteria varied from patient to patient, and that it was difficult to cultivate the microorganisms. However, he was finally able to reproduce them, and the inoculation of the culture in a rabbit first produced symptoms similar to those of beriberi, and then death (Pekelharing, 1889, pp. 16-17). In other rabbits and apes that had been inoculated, no effect was observed – or, sometimes, only a few symptoms.¹² He conjectured that those animals had some kind of immunity.

¹¹ Basile Férís was a professor of the École de Médecine Navale. He published many papers on beriberi, including a review of Brazilian works on the subject.

¹² In later experiments, Pekelharing inoculated 7 rabbits and 44 dogs. After a few days, 6 of the rabbits and 2 of the dogs exhibited degeneration of the nervous system (Pekelharing, 1889, p. 25).

Pekelharing observed the same kind of bacteria in the air, but only at the places where beriberi occurred (Pekelharing, 1889, pp. 17-18). He concluded that the disease was transmitted by the bacteria through the air, and recommended hygienic measures to avoid the disease.

A few months later (July 1887), Pekelharing and Winkler returned to Nederland. Before their return, they produced a second report. Their cultures sometimes produced micrococci, and at other times produced bacteria (Pekelharing, 1889, p. 21). Nowadays, the variability described by Pekelharing would be interpreted as due to his incompetence to isolate a single and definite microorganism. Lacerda, however, added to his translation of Pekelharing's report a remark stating that the same microorganism sometimes assumed one form (micrococcus) and sometimes the other (bacterium). Besides that, Lacerda also commented that he had compared his microorganism with those in preparations sent to him from India by Pekelharing, and that they were identical (Lacerda, in Pekelharing, 1889, p. 23).

The results obtained by Pekelharing in inoculation experiments were highly variable. Some animals exhibited no symptom of beriberi, although their blood was observed to contain micrococci (Pekelharing, 1889, pp. 26-27). He also conjectured that different kinds of bacteria could produce the same disease (Pekelharing, 1889, p. 28) – a conjecture in direct conflict with Koch's postulates. Pekelharing considered, however, as proved beyond all doubt by his experiments, that beriberi was produced by the bacteria he had observed (Pekelharing, 1889, p. 28, pp. 31-32).

Pekelharing did not discover the cause of beriberi. Some years later, two other Dutch investigators working in India gradually unveiled the role of nutrition in beriberi, opening the way to the discovery of vitamins (Ihde & Becker, 1971; Codell Carter, 1977; Bechtel, 1984). One of them, Christiaan Eijkman (1858-1930), had worked with Pekelharing for several years. But that is another story.

A few years later, Lacerda published a new proposal concerning beriberi: he claimed that it was produced by a hematozoon he called *Trypanosoma beriberiano* (Lacerda, 1907, p. 29). A similar allegation had already been supported by another Brazilian researcher, Francisco de Paula Fajardo Júnior (1864-1906) (Fajardo Jr., 1898). Of course, this change of opinion shows that Lacerda recognized that his research of 1883 was wrong – although he never explicitly said that.

8. CONCLUSION

In the long run, the association between microorganisms and beriberi was concluded to be nonexistent. Was it possible, however, at that time, to perceive that Lacerda's work was groundless? Yes, but only highly trained physicians would be able to recognize this. Silva Araújo, writing in 1896, called Lacerda "the notable bacteriologist" – probably implying that Lacerda's bacteriological researches were excellent (Araújo, 1896, pp. 38-39). Sacramento Blake (a physician), writing in 1895 about Lacerda's 1887 book, commented that it was the most complete work on beriberi, from all points of view – that is, nothing relevant was left out of Lacerda's work (Blake, 1883-1902, vol. 3, p. 346).

The microbe theory of diseases was a remarkable step in the development of a scientific medicine. The discovery of some diseases that were caused by specific microorganisms did not prove, however, that all diseases are produced by microbes. In each case, it was necessary to investigate the hypothetical causal relation – and sometimes it could not be confirmed. Unfortunately, the research of microorganisms and their relation to diseases is a very difficult task – and Lacerda was not prepared for it.

The microbe (or parasite) theory of diseases was a landmark in the development of the so-called "Scientific Medicine". It is not possible, however, to divide history in two parts, describing all pre-microbial attempts to understand diseases as non-scientific, and every research associated with microbe theory as scientific. Lacerda and Pekelharing were followers

of the microbe theory, but their works were mistaken and led to no solution to the practical problem – beriberi continued to kill people in Brazil, India and other places.

Let us compare Lacerda's attitude to that of a "pre-scientific" (although later) study: that of the *Junta de Saúde da Armada*. The Navy Health Committee was not blindly attached to any single theory. Its members suspected that several causes could be instrumental in producing beriberi. They tried to cover all known (or suggested) factor by a series of measures that included an improvement of the sailor's food. They accepted the empirical evidence that treatment of beriberi patients at Nova Friburgo produced better results than at the Rio de Janeiro infirmary. On the whole, the *Junta de Saúde da Armada* was less arrogant than the Director of the National Museum, and as a consequence they were more serviceable to the health and welfare of the people.

Let me now add a few remarks concerning the contemporary attitude towards Lacerda, in Brazil. He is sometimes portrayed as a Brazilian pioneer in microbiology, but his mistakes are not described. It is understandable that institutions where he had a leading role – such as the National Museum of Rio de Janeiro, where he attained the position of Director, and the Brazilian Academy of Medicine, where he reached the status of President – are not willing to disclose his shortcomings. Unfortunately, the protecting veil can also be detected in Brazilian papers and books on the history of Medicine (in general) or on the history of microbiology. In my opinion, the embarrassing story behind this and other similar episodes (in Brazil or elsewhere) should never be concealed. There are many lessons about scientists and science that can be learned from the detailed study of mistakes. I will close this paper with one of those historical morals. An adequate study of the history of science should not highlight just the most successful episodes, because this conveys a wrong view on the nature of science. Scientists fail, and for that reason science is not built – and it should not be built – by isolated individuals. Science is a social endeavour, and errors are eventually identified and corrected because there is criticism and discussion in the scientific community. This is a central feature of the nature of science that deserves public appreciation.

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¹³ The year printed in the original cover of this book is 1884; in the title page, however, the publication date appears as 1883.

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